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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The EU-PolarNet 2 project works on crucial tasks for the European polar research activity collectively aiming to consolidate international cooperation and better coordination of common efforts. This process needs good internal corporate communication with the project partners and external communication with the stakeholders and the general public. This obligation is a key task within EU-PolarNet 2's Work Package (WP) 5.

The Second Progress Report on dissemination activities (Deliverable No. 5.6) of EU-PolarNet 2 – was prepared by the UoS-CPS with the contribution and support of all EU-PolarNet 2 partners. It covers the period from September 1, 2021, to September 30, 2022, i.e. the deliverable comprises all dissemination activities of EU-PolarNet 2 in the second year of the project realisation.

The content presents dissemination activities at conferences and events (section 2), webinars (section 3), and online outreach via the webpage, newsletter, and social media channels (section 4). Special attention is paid to the new multifunctional *Catalyst Platform* especially designed and implemented for this project (section 5). Similarly, two unique publications of the project: '*Catalogue of National Polar Programmes and Other Large-Scale Programmes*' and '*Directory of European Polar Research Funding Programmes*' are presented as well (section 6).

1 Introduction

The most important aim of the EU-PolarNet 2 project is to enhance international cooperation in the European polar research activity and a better coordination of common efforts. A way to achieve planned tasks needs good internal corporate communication with the project partners and external communication with the stakeholders and the general public. This obligation is a key assignment within EU-PolarNet 2's Work Package (WP) 5. The dissemination activities presented in the following sections describe the strategic and targeted measures with which the work of the project and its results and outcomes are promoted to a wide range of recipients and audiences. It describes communication and dissemination activities at conferences and events (section 2), webinars (section 3), and online outreach via the webpage, newsletter, and social media channels (section 4). It is worth to note the new multifunctional *Catalyst Platform* especially designed and implemented for the EU-PolarNet 2 (section 5). Special attention is paid to two new and unique publications of the project: '*Catalogue of National Polar Programmes and Other Large-Scale Programmes*' and '*Directory of European Polar Research Funding Programmes*' are presented as well (section 6).

2 Dissemination at conferences and events

Members of the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium have actively promoted the realisation, a stage results and progress of the project at national, European and international conferences and workshops between September 2021 and September 2022. The formula of the meetings was limited due to the Covid-19 disease and varied from online, through hybrid, to in-person meetings in the last months. The table below lists the dissemination activities at meetings and events during the indicated period. Most of these events are also described on <https://eu-polarnet.eu/events-2/>.

TABLE I. Conferences and workshops with EU-PolarNet 2 contribution.

Name of event	Date	Location	Activity	Representative/s	Source/s
ESA Polar Science Cluster Collocation Meeting 2021	15-17/09/2021	online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Carlo Barbante, Vito Vitale, Chiara Venier, Nicoletta Ademollo, Warren Cairns, Angelina Lo Giudice	https://eo4society.esa.int/resource/esa-polar-science-cluster-collocation-meeting-2021/
Southern Ocean Decade & Polar Data Forum IV	20-24/09/2021	online	Participation to a conference	Dragomir Mateev, Rositsa Yaneva, Lubomir Kenderov	https://www.sodecade.org/event/southern-ocean-decade-polar-data-forum-week-2021/ https://polar-data-forum.org/
Arctic Circle Assembly 2021	14-17/10/2021	Reykjavik, Iceland	Participation to a conference	Marta Chmielewska, Egill Thor Nielsson Elżbieta Łepkowska	https://www.arcticcircle.org/assemblies/2021-arctic-circle-assembly
EU-PolarNet 2 General Assembly	25-27/10/2021	online	Organisation of a Conference	All partners	Deliverable D7.5 Organisation and minutes of the second EU-PolarNet 2 General Assembly. CONSORTIUM ONLY.
EPB Autumn Plenary Meeting	27-29/10/2021	hybrid: Brussels, Belgium / online	Participation to a meeting	EPB team: J Nolan, R Badhe, P Elshout Several national representatives & EU-PolarNet 2 partners	-
26th UN Climate Change Conference of the Parties (COP26) & COP26 EU Pavilion side	31/10 – 12/11/2021	Glasgow/Brussels	Organisation of a workshop; Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Elaina Ford, J Nolan, R Badhe, P Elshout	https://ukcop26.org/ https://eu-polarnet.eu/cop26-eu-pavilion-side-event-polar-warming-global-warming/

event: “Polar warming, global warming”					
EU Arctic Forum and Indigenous People's Dialogue	10-11/11/2021	Hybrid: Brussels, Belgian / online	Participation to a conference	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Elaina Ford, Annette Scheepstra, J Nolan, R Badhe, P Elshout	https://europa.eu/newsroom/event/eu-arctic-forum-and-indigenous-peoples%E2%80%99-dialogue_en
38th International Polar Symposium	18-20/11/2021	Toruń, Poland	Participation to a conference	Jacek Jania Piotr Głowacki Marta Chmielewska Elżbieta Łepkowska	https://polarsymposium2020.umk.pl/pages/main_page/?langu=en
Scientific Symposium 'The cold is getting hot': From Arctic to Antarctic'	24-25/02/2022	Monaco	Participation to a conference	Nicole Biebow, Antonio Quesada, Renuka Badhe	https://www.the-polarinitiative.org/en/index
One Ocean Summit 2022	9-11/02/2022	Brest, France	Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	Nicole Biebow	https://www.cgiar.org/news-events/event/2022-one-ocean-summit/
Arctic Science Summit Week 2022	26/03 – 1/04/2022	Hybrid: Tromsø, Norway / online	Participation to a conference Organisation of a workshop	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Veronica Willmott, Gonçalo Vieira, Maria Teresa Cabrita, Joana Baptista, Antonio Quesada, Kirsi Latola, Ozgun Oktar, Jon Børre Ørbæk, Piotr Głowacki, Joseph Nolan, Pjotr Elshout, in presence: Vito Vitale and Chiara Venier; Carlo Barbante, Nicoletta Ademollo, Warren Cairns, Angelina Lo Giudice, Annette Scheepstra Christina Abildgaard, Ingunn Borlaug Lid, Oda Bjelland	https://iasc.info/events/2-arctic-science-summit-week-2022
Arctic Observing Summit	30/03 – 1/04/2022	Tromsø, Norway	Participation to a conference	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Veronica Willmott, Piotr Głowacki, J Nolan, R Badhe, P Elshout	https://arcticobservingsummit.org/summits/aos-2022/
European Polar Board Plenary Meeting	5-6/04/2022	online	Participation to a conference	J Nolan, R Badhe, P Elshout, Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Elaina Ford, Kirsi Latola	
High North Dialogue	6-7/04/2022	Hybrid: Bodø, Norway /online	Participation to a conference	A. Scheepstra	https://app.myonvent.com/event/high-north-dialogue-2022

					https://www.highnorthdialogue.no/
Arctic Frontiers 2022 Pathways	8-11/05/2022	Hybrid: Tromsø, Norway / online	Participation to a conference	Jon Børre Ørbæk	https://www.arcticfrontiers.com/arctic-frontiers-2022/
Living Planet Symposium	23-27/05/2022	Bonn, Germany	Plenary presentation	N. Biebow, A. Strobel	https://lps22.eu/
XLIV Antarctic Treaty Consultive Meeting (44th ATCM)	23/05 – 06/06/2022	Berlin, Germany	Participation to a conference	A. Quesada	https://atcm44-berlin.de/en/0_atcm-xliv-english/
EU-PolarNet 2 Workshop 'Recommendations Towards An Integrated Polar Observing System'	7/06/2022	online	Organisation of a workshop	H. Savela, J. Larsen, S. Scory, P. Elshout, A. Strobel	https://youtu.be/Rjx50tAPSrc
EU Polar Cluster Meeting	21-22/06/2022	Brussels, Belgium	Organisation of a workshop	E. Ford, L. Green, N. Biebow, A. Strobel, R. Badhe, P. Elshout, J. Nolan, K. Latola, A. Scheepstra, C. Venier, J. Baptista	https://eu-polarnet.eu/docs/d1-6-first-progress-report-on-activities-and-achievements-of-the-eu-polar-cluster/
The Ocean Conference	27/06-1/07/2022	Lisbon, Portugal	Participation to a conference	R. Badhe	https://www.un.org/en/conferences/ocean2022
Research Cooperation From Pole To Pole / the All-Atlantic Ministerial and Stakeholder Conference	12/07/2022	Washington , USA	Participation to a conference Organisation of a workshop in the residence of the Portuguese Embassy	N. Biebow, R. Badhe, A. Strobel	https://allatlantic2022.com/?avia_forced_reroute=1#forum
SMM international maritime trade fair	03-06/09/2022	Hamburg, Germany	Organisation of EU Polar Cluster booth; survey for 2nd transdisciplinary stakeholder workshop	K. Latola, C. Valentin, C. Venier, H. Sevestre, A. Strobel	https://www.smm-hamburg.com/
10th SCAR Open Science Conference	1-10/08/2022	online	Participation to a conference	R. Badhe	https://scar2022.org/
EU-PolarNet 2 General Assembly & Retreat	13-15/09/2022	Sofia, Bulgaria	Organisation of a conference and workshop	All partners	D7.6 Minutes of General Assembly due 30 November 2022

3 Webinars

EU-PolarNet 2 has organised three important webinars. A recording of them are available on YouTube. More information about the webinars can be found on event's websites (sources in the below table).

TABLE II. Webinars organized by EU-PolarNet 2.

Name of webinar	Date	Organiser/Chair/Presenter	Attendees	Source/s
The new EU Arctic Policy and Research and Innovation	24/11/2021	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Annette Scheepstra, Renuka Badhe, Joseph Nolan, Pjotr Elshout	60	https://eu-polarnet.eu/webinar-new-eu-arctic-policy/
Webinar: Who owns the Arctic? – an Introduction to Arctic Governance	9/06/2022	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Volker Rachold	40	https://eu-polarnet.eu/webinar-who-owns-the-arctic/ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jGPo6d8zEJk
Catalyst Platform launch webinar	30/06/2022	Antonio Quesada, Nicole Biebow	20	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-J-lckjzeE4

4 Online outreach

4.1 Webpage

The EU-PolarNet 2 webpage remains the leading and central online dissemination source for dynamically developing social media. This platform is raising appreciation of the project, sharing information related to the work of the consortium and cooperation partners. The webpage promotes also upcoming events. The targeted audience ranges from the broad science community, to representatives of the industry, NGOs, interest groups, national and international policy makers, media and the general public. To catch the interest and demands of the various audience sections, the website offers both a wide range of informational data on the project aims and progress, and regularly updated contents, such as announcements and news.

The implementation of EU-PolarNet 2 website was done by the IGOT-UL team with the support of the AWI team in December 2020. It is one of the deliverables (D5.1.) of the WP5 - Policy Advice, Dissemination, Communication - Providing evidence-based policy advice. The architecture of the website (eu-polarnet.eu) was structured inside the Wordpress system and assigned to a domain provided by the company Domínios.pt. inside the Wordpress system. A set of plugins were installed with the aim of strengthen security, facilitate navigation, organise the databases, improving the aesthetic visage. It also has a restricted area for the internal project communication. The website is constantly updated. Information about current webpage structure and statistics can be found in Annex 7.3.

Fig.1. Screenshot of the homepage of the EU-PolarNet 2: <https://eu-polarnet.eu/>.

4.1 Newsletter

Quarterly newsletters were established. In the reporting period, three of them have been published and broadly distributed via e-mails. The addressees of news from the EU-PolarNet 2 are the project consortium members, the EU Polar Cluster partners and the wider European polar research community.

Newsletters provide a glimpse on activities and events coming up in the future. To receive the newsletter parties and individuals interested in this way of dissemination of polar news can register at the webpage (<https://eu-polarnet.eu/newsletter/>). Recently, the newsletter has 888 recipients.

Fig.2. Newsletter webpage of the EU-PolarNet 2: <https://eu-polarnet.eu/newsletter/>.

4.1.1 Newsletter - December 2021

The fourth newsletter was written by the IGOT team and distributed in December 2021. It is available at <https://eu-polarnet.eu/newsletter-december-2021/>.

Newsletter content:

- [News from EU-PolarNet 2](#)
 - [Entering the second year – EU-PolarNet 2’s second General Assembly](#)
 - [Webinar “The new Arctic Policy”](#)
 - [COP26 EU Pavilion side event: “Polar warming, global warming”](#)

- EU-PolarNet 2 Service Calls
- Coming soon: ‘Catalogue of national Polar programmes and other large-scale programmes’ and ‘Directory of Polar research funding programmes in Europe’
- EU Polar Cluster News
- Partner highlights on polar research
 - A sensational discovery: Traces of rainforests in West Antarctica
 - World Press Photo Award for AWI Photographer
 - 3rd National Call for Polar Research in Bulgaria
 - Beyond EPICA field campaign 2021/22
 - The National Centre for Climate Research in Denmark
 - The International Arctic Hub
 - Launch of the College on Polar and Extreme Environments (POLAR2E)
 - Marine plastic pollution in the Arctic
 - 30th anniversary of the icebreaker Oden at the North Pole
 - Launch of Swiss polar programmes
 - The Arctic Century expedition 2021
 - How climate change affects the Arctic: ocean, land and biodiversity
 - Human health risks in the Arctic
 - Estonians to sail to Arctic to draw attention to climate change
- Highlights of Polar programmes
 - A glimpse on Swiss Polar Institute
 - A glimpse on Institute of Geology, Tallinn University of Technology
- Upcoming events

4.1.2 Newsletter - March 2022

The fifth newsletter was written by the IGOT team and distributed in March 2022. It is available at <https://eu-polarnet.eu/newsletter-march-2022/>.

Newsletter content:

- News from EU-PolarNet 2
 - The second EU-PolarNet 2 Service Call is open!
 - ‘Catalogue of national Polar programmes and other large-scale programmes’ and ‘Directory of Polar research funding programmes in Europe’
- EU Polar Cluster News
- Partner highlights on polar research
 - Research programme into Antarctic tourism
 - Memorandum of Understanding signed between Spain and Turkey
 - The Sixth Turkish Antarctic Expedition (TAE-VI)
 - The 5th Polar Science Workshop & The 2nd Polar Science Festival
 - New RV Belgica enhances Belgian marine polar research

- Webinar: The new EU Arctic Policy and Research and Innovation
- The Southern Ocean on Europe's shores - climate impacts, sea level rise, and the marine environment
- Greenland Integrated Observing System (GIOS)
- World's largest fish breeding area discovered in Antarctica
- Reactivation of the Polish A.B. Dobrowolski Polar Station in the Bunge Hills Oasis, East Antarctica.
- Highlights of Polar programmes
 - A glimpse on the Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany
 - A glimpse on Bulgarian Antarctic Institute
 - A glimpse on the Faroe Marine Research Institute
 - A glimpse on the Netherlands Polar Programme
 - A glimpse on the Swedish Polar Research Secretariat
 - Upcoming events

4.1.3 Newsletter - July 2022

The sixth newsletter was written by the IGOT team and distributed in July 2022. It is available at <https://eu-polarnet.eu/newsletter-june-2022/>.

Newsletter content:

- News from EU-PolarNet 2
 - Webinar: Who owns the Arctic? – an Introduction to Arctic Governance
 - Workshop 'Recommendations towards an Integrated Polar Observing System'
 - Catalyst platform launched
 - 'Catalogue of national Polar programmes and other large-scale programmes' and 'Directory of Polar research funding programmes in Europe' published!
- EU Polar Cluster News
 - EU Polar Cluster meeting in Brussels
- Partner highlights on polar research
 - New SEES.nl expedition to Spitsbergen in July
 - Micro- and nanoplastic from the atmosphere is polluting the ocean
 - Southern Ocean floor mapped in greatest detail ever
 - Start of Swiss Flagship Initiatives in Pamir and Greenland: a new phase for Swiss polar science
 - Konrad Steffen Grant for enhanced Swiss-Greenlandic research collaboration
 - The tenth Portuguese flight supporting the Antarctic Summer season 2021-22
 - Estonian Arctic Policy
 - Geomorphological processes shape Arctic plants
 - First ice core drilling campaign of Beyond EPICA successfully completed

- Czech Arctic running research projects at the Centre for Polar Ecology, Faculty of Science, University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice
- The first in Poland strategy of polar policy on the governmental level
- Highlights of Polar programmes
- A glimpse on IGOT and the Portuguese Polar Community
- Upcoming events

4.2 Social Media

The social media arteries of communication are very effective. Such channels are giving EU-PolarNet 2 better visibility and engage regularly the broad science community, stakeholders and a general public on the immediate basis. The project is present on social media with several accounts (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn). The Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn accounts are managed through the Crowdfire platform (<https://www.crowdfireapp.com>). The platform permits the formulation and planning of publications made simultaneously on the listed above channels. There is also possible the making of quarterly reports with the statistical analysis of the social media accounts.

4.2.1 Twitter

The Twitter channel can be accessed at <https://twitter.com/eupolarnet>. At the time the EU-PolarNet channel has 2631 followers (by 14.10.2022). [+319/throughout the year]

4.2.2 Instagram

EU-PolarNet's instagram account can be accessed at <https://www.instagram.com/eupolarnet/>. At the time the account has 686 subscribers (by 14.10.2022). [+250/throughout the year]

4.2.3 Facebook

EU-PolarNet's facebook page can be accessed at <https://www.facebook.com/groups/1442027029433733/?ref=bookmarks>. To date the group has 1967 members (by 14.10.2021). [+22/throughout the year]

4.2.4 LinkedIn

EU-PolarNet's LinkedIn page can be accessed at <https://www.linkedin.com/in/eu-polarnet-3a21bb207/>. Currently the group has 107 members (by 14.10.2022). [+9/throughout the year]

4.2.5 YouTube

EU-PolarNet's YouTube channel can be accessed at

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqEzHkh6Q-ucxOFtd7UWHDA/> featured. At the time 39 videos are available and the channel has 83 subscribers (by 14.10.2022) [+28/throughout the year].

Recordings of some events organised jointly with the EPB are also available on the EPB's YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBZM37I_50Hb0g2AYcgqAsg/feature).

Fig.3. Screenshot of the YouTube channel of the EU-PolarNet 2: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqEzHkh6Q-ucxOFtd7UWHDA/>.

5 Catalyst Platform

The launch of the Catalyst platform, developed by EU-PolarNet 2, was a huge success within the European polar community.

The Catalyst platform will accommodate a continuous information exchange and an interactive room as a discussion forum for the Polar community to identify synergies and develop partnerships within Europe. It will also serve as catalyst where researchers, stake- and rightsholders, industry, and others discuss new ideas and big collaborative initiatives involving several parties.

The platform was launched on Thursday, 30 June 2020. Everyone is welcome to visit the Catalyst Platform (<https://polarcatalyst.eu/>) to share resources and join the discussions.

A recording of the launch Catalyst Platform on June 30, 2022, is available on YouTube:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-J-lckjzeE4&t=124s>.

Fig.4. Catalyst Platform the welcome screen: <https://polarcatalyst.eu/>.

6 Publication

The result of joint project activities is the release of two important documents: “Catalogue of National Polar Programmes and Other Large-Scale Programmes” and “Directory of European Polar Research Funding Programmes”. They present the European polar research organizational landscape and are very useful for scientists, decision-makers and stakeholders.

6.1 Catalogue of National Polar Programmes and Other Large-Scale Programmes

The "Catalogue of National Polar Programmes and Other Large-scale programmes" provides an over-view about the responsibilities, research focus and governance structures in European countries performing polar research. The heterogeneity of European National Polar programmes makes this catalogue an essential tool to facilitate the communication and to support synergistic joint actions among the national programmes.

This catalogue is the result of a survey sent to the entire EU-PolarNet 2 consortium, based on a wide range of questions. The information received reflects the different approaches of each country to polar policy and re-search. The result is a structured, but diverse document giving every country the opportunity to gain insight in each other pro-cedures.

Citation: *EU-PolarNet 2 (2022) Catalogue of national Polar programmes and other large-scale programmes (Eds. Blunt M, Mateev D, Pimpirev, C, Quesada A, Strobel A, Biebow N). 76 pp. Bremerhaven: Alfred Wegener Institute. <https://zenodo.org/record/7003911#.Y0muQ2Q9cVE>*

6.2 Directory of European Polar Research Funding Programmes

The EU-PolarNet2 launched the “Directory of European Polar Research Funding Programme” which provides an overview about the governance, strategies, and procedures of polar research funding in Europe fundamental for a strong European polar research environment.

Citation: *EU-PolarNet 2 Consortium (2022) Directory of European Polar Research funding programmes (eds: Vancauwenberghe, M., Deleu, P., Ørbæk, J.B., Strobel, A. and Biebow, N). Bremerhaven, Germany, EU-PolarNet 2, 58pp. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6399293>*

7 Annexes

7.1 Webpackage

7.1.1 Webpage structure

- About - presentation of the objectives and partners, facts and figures and structure of the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium and the history of the EU-PolarNet 1:
 - Objectives
 - Partners
 - Facts and Figures
 - Consortium Structure
 - History
- Thematic Activities - a summary of the Work Packages with the identification of the leaders and main tasks framed by a short presentation;
- Achievements - the public deliverables from the EU-PolarNet 1 and 2, organised by Work Package:
 - 2020-2024
 - 2015-2020
- Communication - publications and event documentation from the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium. Moreover, information and a link to the Catalyst Platform:
 - Publications
 - Event Documentation
 - Catalyst Platform
- News - the latest news was presented briefly, and also newsletters with the possibility of sign up:
 - EU-PolarNet news
 - Newsletter
- Events - the future and past events with special interest for the EU-PolarNet 2 community;
- Call for services - support from the European Polar Community to develop ideas for concrete research activities in accordance with six research needs of the European Polar Research Programme:
 - Call for services
 - First call
 - Second call
 - Third call

7.1.2 Webpage statistic

From September 2021 to September 2022, the webpage had a total of 9372 visitors [5721 in the last, 1st EU-PolarNet 2 report on dissemination activities: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006359>]. The

months with the higher activity were June 2022 (the launching of the Catalyst platform: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-J-lckjzeE4&t=124s>). On average, the visits to the website had a duration of 2 min 20s. Most of the visitors have reached the website directly with the url.

Fig.5. Number of visitors to the EU-PolarNet 2 webpage (Sept, 2021 – Sept, 2022).

Fig.6. Visitors origin to the EU-PolarNet 2 webpage (Sept, 2021 – Sept, 2022).

Regarding the origin of the visitors, 12% (1137) reach the website from the United States, 10% (979) from Germany, 8% (781) from Norway and 6% (541-570) from France, Finland and Netherlands.

Fig.7. Map of the EU-PolarNet 2 website visitors (Sept, 2021 – Sept, 2022).

Moving to the activity inside the website, the homepage was the one with the higher number of pageviews (4847) followed by the “About” page (1426) and by the “Call of Services” page (1231).

Fig.7. Activity inside the EU-PolarNet 2 website – procentage of pageviews (Sept, 2021 – Sept, 2022).

“Catalogue of National Polar Programmes and Other Large-Scale Programmes” and “Directory of European Polar Research Funding Programmes” were very popular for downloading (192 and 142 times).

Fig.8. Documents downloaded from the EU-PolarNet website (Sept, 2021 – Sept, 2022).